

THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TEACHING TASKS IN THE PROVISION OF ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION TO ELEMENTARY STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article covers current issues of the development of the educational system, ways of providing environmental education to primary school students, mechanisms for using innovative educational tasks in the provision of environmental education.

Keywords: primary education, ecology, environmental education, environment, water, educational assignment, ecological culture, plants, animals, birds

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАДАНИЙ В ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОМ ВОСПИТАНИИ МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье освещаются актуальные вопросы развития системы образования, пути экологического воспитания учащихся начальных классов, механизмы использования инновационных учебных заданий в экологическом воспитании.

Ключевые слова: начальное образование, экология, экологическое воспитание, окружающая среда, вода, учебное задание, экологическая культура, растения, животные, птицы

The future of Uzbekistan is associated with the level of education of the younger generation, and the emphasis on the issue of development of the education system at the policy level is considered an important task of each state.

It is becoming an urgent issue that the reforms carried out in our country in recent years regularly improve the system of continuing education, as in developed countries.

At the present stage of the development of the educational system, there are problems with changes in the field of socio-economic relations, new priorities in directing students to the profession[1]. On the one hand, the formation of a comprehensively harmonious personality in any secondary schools, on the other hand, led to the fact that in our country students who are always ready to study do not study. Currently, the state of environmental education is of greatest concern. Of course, ecology is the independent work of students using various sources of knowledge for students studying in these areas with multimedia courses developed by teachers:

- self-study and cross-learning;
- educational and business Games.

Thus, ecological and valecological knowledge develops a person in all areas of his activity. In our opinion, it is impossible to form a common culture of students without this knowledge.

Thus, the implementation of various directions of environmental education in students will help to fully meet the educational needs of schoolchildren, attract them to practical activities.

Today's life is not limited to individual educational work, but requires them to be integrated into a chain of continuous environmental actions, combined with Labor, Social and environmental education.

Filled with local materials and appropriately presented Environmental Information makes sure that it is necessary to urgently help nature, there is a desire to at least partially compensate for what we have received from it for a long time. If the reader understands that his well-being, the next day, the happiness of himself, relatives and friends depends on the cleanliness of water and air, a spring, a small grove, a clear help to the lower floor, he will join the ranks of conservationists and friends.

The main meaning of environmental education work is precisely practical environmental activity. Taking care of nature, its well-being, purity, schoolchildren are interested in this profession, in the process of which they have observability, cognitive interest activity, patriotism, love and respect for the motherland increase.

Our country is rich in natural resources. It is very interesting to observe natural objects, but we must not forget that nature is very weak, it must be protected and

appreciated. The objects of environmental activity are the earth, water, air, animals, birds, plants of all sources of human life. The needs of the region, local conditions determine the direction, type, organization and implementation of environmental educational work, such as the movement of “green” and “blue” groups, young friends of the Forest, Bird and animal advocates, rare plant breeders [2].

Increasing the role of the regional component, taking into account the peculiarities of the area where schoolchildren live, can be carried out by teachers of local ecology, biology and geography in secondary schools. After all, ecology is an interdisciplinary science. To understand the modern ecological situation, a person must have knowledge in all subjects of the natural-scientific cycle (geography, biology, ecology, chemistry, physics- (natural sciences)). The formation of urban schoolchildren’s ideas about the territorial diversity of the world in natural, economic, social, environmental, ethnic and other aspects at the local level (their own city, their own district) makes it possible to make the process of teaching ecology more meaningful for children, increase the level of general culture and expand local knowledge about their hometown.

The landscape around the school, the quarter, the urban and rural area and the surrounding town, becomes a rural scientific exploration laboratory. By participating in the planned work, students will have a holistic picture of the world, make sure of the need to know environmental laws and develop creative independence[3].

In addition, when teaching natural sciences to elementary students, it is advisable to use the following tasks in the course of the lesson in the formation of ecological culture in them (figure 1-2).

Figure 1. In the care of room plants, which of the objects given in the image below is used?

Figure 2. Which of those given from the image below will we have to preserve? Mark based on numbers.

Task 3. Complete the answer to these asked questions.

Diamond shelter:

tree where the nest is located _____

the height at which the nest is located _____

shape of the nest

dimensions

Thus, the implementation of various directions of environmental education in the course of the lesson will help to fully meet the educational needs of schoolchildren, attract them to practical activities.

As a conclusion, it can be said that the use of innovative educational tasks in the provision of environmental education to primary school students causes the formation of an ecological culture in them, the development of a positive attitude towards ecosystems.

REFERENCES:

- 1.The decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated July 28, 2017 PQ-3160 "on improving the efficiency of spiritual and educational work and raising the development of the sphere to a new level"
2. D.Muminova, M.Handasheva, N.To ' rayeva, Z.Yulchieva. Natural Science and its teaching methodology. Textbook. 2023. – B.118
- 3.Zhuraev R, Zunnunov A. Integration of educational subjects in the educational process. Oriental publishing. - T.: 2005. - B. 52